

1 **Solute carrier activation during resistance to chemotherapy in TNBC cells.**

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6 Multiple SLC factors were engaged in human TNBC, including a possible role for alternative channels in
7 MDR, and nutrient/biochemical utilization during resistance. Solute carriers identified included *SLC9A1*
8 and *SLC26A2*.

9 Citations

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